

Explore

Group

Case Processing Summary

Group	Valid	Cases		Total			
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
SmlArena	Beacon	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	100.0%
	Random	15	100.0%	0	0.0%	15	100.0%
MedArena	Beacon	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	100.0%
	Random	15	100.0%	0	0.0%	15	100.0%
LrgArena	Beacon	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	100.0%
	Random	15	100.0%	0	0.0%	15	100.0%

Descriptives

Group	Statistic	Std. Error		
SmlArena	Beacon	Mean	155.595240	4.3223580
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	143.594450	
		Upper Bound	167.596030	
	5% Trimmed Mean	156.108061		
	Median	158.205500		
	Variance	93.414		
	Std. Deviation	9.6650862		
	Minimum	138.7540		
	Maximum	163.2057		
	Range	24.4517		
	Interquartile Range	13.5258		
	Skewness	-1.944	.913	
	Kurtosis	4.078	2.000	
	Random	Mean	153.375065	37.6587514
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	72.605076	
		Upper Bound	234.145053	
5% Trimmed Mean		138.567262		
Median		111.702700		
Variance		21272.723		
Std. Deviation		145.8517170		
Minimum		30.9519		
Maximum		542.3387		
Range		511.3868		
Interquartile Range		207.9105		
Skewness		1.429	.580	
Kurtosis		2.310	1.121	
MedArena		Beacon	Mean	265.187440

Descriptives

Group			Statistic	Std. Error	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	253.965201		
		Upper Bound	276.409679		
	5% Trimmed Mean		265.137994		
	Median		268.006400		
	Variance		81.687		
	Std. Deviation		9.0380643		
	Minimum		254.0602		
	Maximum		277.2047		
	Range		23.1445		
	Interquartile Range		16.2462		
	Skewness		.070	.913	
	Kurtosis		-.857	2.000	
	Random	Mean		220.449495	42.0788456
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	130.199347	
Upper Bound			310.699643		
5% Trimmed Mean		207.664620			
Median		165.605800			
Variance		26559.439			
Std. Deviation		162.9706684			
Minimum		65.8027			
Maximum		605.2240			
Range		539.4213			
Interquartile Range		199.8435			
Skewness		1.286	.580		
Kurtosis		.843	1.121		
LrgArena		Beacon	Mean	329.071980	9.7856918
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	301.902544	
	Upper Bound		356.241416		
	5% Trimmed Mean		328.000600		
	Median		317.045200		
	Variance		478.799		
	Std. Deviation		21.8814720		
	Minimum		312.9954		
	Maximum		364.4334		
	Range		51.4380		
	Interquartile Range		36.5662		
	Skewness		1.418	.913	
	Kurtosis		1.258	2.000	
		Random	Mean	256.412199	29.3186004
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	193.530055	
Upper Bound			319.294343		
5% Trimmed Mean		255.443127			
Median		259.008800			

Descriptives

Group		Statistic	Std. Error
	Variance	12893.705	
	Std. Deviation	113.5504512	
	Minimum	96.3016	
	Maximum	433.9661	
	Range	337.6645	
	Interquartile Range	238.9316	
	Skewness	-.046	.580
	Kurtosis	-1.426	1.121

Tests of Normality

	Group	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
SmlArena	Beacon	.382	5	.016	.762	5	.039
	Random	.201	15	.106	.822	15	.007
MedArena	Beacon	.222	5	.200*	.952	5	.753
	Random	.202	15	.100	.846	15	.015
LrgArena	Beacon	.309	5	.135	.812	5	.100
	Random	.155	15	.200*	.928	15	.251

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

SmlArena

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

SmlArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for

Group= Beacon

Frequency Stem & Leaf

1.00 Extremes (<=139)

2.00 15 . 78

2.00 16 . 03

Stem width: 10.0000

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

SmlArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for

Group= Random

Frequency Stem & Leaf

7.00 0 . 3333337

3.00 1 . 149

3.00 2 . 246

1.00 3.0
1.00 Extremes (>=542)

Stem width: 100.0000
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of SmlArena

for Group= Beacon

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of SmlArena

for Group= Random

MedArena

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

MedArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Beacon

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
2.00	25 . 48
2.00	26 . 88
1.00	27 . 7

Stem width: 10.0000
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

MedArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Random

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
3.00	0 . 669
6.00	1 . 002369
2.00	2 . 04
1.00	3 . 0
2.00	4 . 27
1.00	Extremes (>=605)

Stem width: 100.0000
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

LrgArena

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

LrgArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Beacon

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
4.00	3 . 1113
1.00	3 . 6

Stem width: 100.0000
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

LrgArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Random

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
1.00	0 . 9
4.00	1 . 1117
4.00	2 . 0457
5.00	3 . 24588
1.00	4 . 3

Stem width: 100.0000
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of LrgArena
for Group= Beacon

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of LrgArena
for Group= Random

